

Studies on the Use of Acetothioacetanilide as a Reagent for the Gravimetric Determination of Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II)

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Nickel(II) and cobalt(II) have been precipitated from solutions of pH 6.4-6.9 and 6.7-12.0 as their acetothioacetanilide complexes of formulae $Ni(C_{10}H_{10}ONS)_2$ and $Co(C_{10}H_{10}ONS)_2$ which can be weighed after drying at 110° and 80° respectively. The relative standard deviations are $\pm 0.46\%$ and $\pm 0.45\%$. The composition of the complexes have been studied by elemental analysis, thermogravimetric studies and magnetic measurements. Separation from several diverse ions, including Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , VO^{2+} , AsO_4^{3-} and MoO_4^{2-} have been effected using tartrate or sulphosalicylic acid as masking agent. Nickel content of a few samples of stainless steel has been determined using ion-exchangers for preliminary separations as masking of the foreign ions was not possible when they were present in large excess.

ALTHOUGH the most common reagent for the gravimetric determination of nickel is dimethylglyoxime¹, various thiocompounds²⁻⁵, have been used for the same purpose. Several thiocompounds⁶⁻⁹ have also been recommended for the gravimetric estimation of cobalt.

The object of this investigation is to study the applicability of the ligands capable of forming chelates through one oxygen and one sulphur atom for the determination of nickel(II) and cobalt(II). A new reagent, acetothioacetanilide, $CH_3CO.CH_2.CS.NH.C_6H_5$ has been found to give weighable complexes with both.

Experimental

Acetothioacetanilide solution: The reagent was prepared following the method due to Barnikow, Kunzek and Richter¹⁰. Fresh solutions of the reagent were prepared by dissolving 0.20 to 0.35g of it in minimum volume of 2N aqueous ammonia.

Nickel(II) solution: Pure nickel chloride (G.R., E. Merck) was dissolved in very dilute hydrochloric acid and the metal content was determined gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime¹.

Cobalt(II) solution: A stock solution of cobalt(II) sulphate (A.R., B.D.H.) was prepared and cobalt was estimated with α -nitroso- β -naphthol¹¹.

All the other chemicals were of analytical grade.

Apparatus: A Cambridge bench model pH-meter was used to control the pH-values and the magnetic measurements were carried out in a standard Guoy balance. The thermogravimetric studies were carried out with a Photorecording Metriplex Derivatigraph OD-102 (Hungary).

Procedure for nickel(II): An aliquot of the nickel solution containing 8 to 20 mg of nickel was diluted to about 125 ml with water, mixed with 2g of ammonium chloride, the pH was adjusted to 2-3, and heated to 45-55°. The reagent solution was added and the pH was raised to 6.4-6.9 with aqueous ammonia (2N) to precipitate the brown complex. After 15 minutes, the complex was filtered through a sintered glass crucible (No. 4) and washed with warm (50°) water adjusted to pH 6.5. The precipitate was dried at 100-110° and weighed as $Ni(C_{10}H_{10}ONS)_2$ containing 13.25% of the metal. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL OR COBALT

Metal ion taken	Weight (mg)	Wt. of complex (mg)	Metal ion found (mg)	Rel. error (%)
Ni ²⁺	8.62	66.00 ; 65.70	8.75 ; 8.71	+1.52 ; +1.08
	14.37	108.30 ; 109.20	14.35 ; 14.47	-0.10 ; +0.73
	20.11	150.95 ; 152.55	20.02 ; 20.23	-0.45 ; +0.59
Co ²⁺	7.68	82.83 ; 82.79	7.67 ; 7.66	-0.23 ; -0.28
	9.60	103.20 ; 103.30	9.55 ; 9.56	-0.53 ; -0.44
	13.44	144.80 ; 144.50	13.40 ; 13.38	-0.30 ; -0.44

Nickel was also determined in several samples of steel (Table 2) after preliminary separations using ion-exchangers¹².

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL IN STAINLESS STEEL

Composition, (%)	Ni found, (%)	Rel. error, (%)
Ni, 9.48 ; C, 0.10 ; Cr, 17.51	9.52 ; 9.48	+0.42 ; Nil
Ni, 13.43 ; C, 0.06 ; Cr, 16.47	13.62 ; 13.56	+1.49 ; +0.97
Mo, 2.70		

Procedure for cobalt(II): A known quantity of

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the stock solution containing 6-13 mg of cobalt(II) was mixed with 1-1.5g of ammonium chloride, diluted to 125ml and the pH was adjusted to 3-4. The mixture was heated (45-50°) and the reagent solution was added. The pH was raised to 6.7-12.0 with aqueous ammonia. A green precipitate was formed immediately which was left on water-bath for 15 mins at 45-50° before filtration. The complex was washed with warm (40-45°) water of pH 7.0 and weighed after drying at 80° for 90 mins. The cobalt content was calculated using a factor 0.0926. The results are given in Table 1.

The proper masking agent was added before the addition of the reagent when separation of nickel or cobalt from diverse ions were effected.

Results and Discussion

Properties and composition of the complexes : The nickel complex was brown-grey in colour, while the cobalt complex was green. Both the complexes were soluble in common organic solvents. An ethanolic solution of the reagent could also be used provided the final concentration of ethanol did not exceed 5%.

Both the complexes were dried and analysed for nitrogen by Kjeldahl's (micro) method and also for the metal content^{1,11} after decomposing the complexes. The experimental results, Ni(Calc. 13.25%, found 13.16, 13.23%), N(Calc. 6.32%, found 6.22, 6.35%) and Co(Calc. 9.26%, found 9.29, 9.27%), N(Calc. 6.60%, found 6.60, 6.62%) indicated the formulae to be

Magnetic Data and thermal decomposition studies : The nickel(II)-bis-acetothioacetanilide chelate was found to be diamagnetic indicating a square planar arrangement. The cobalt(II) complex on the other hand was paramagnetic (μ , 2.98 B.M.), corresponding to octahedral configuration.

Both the complexes were mixed with appropriate quantities of aluminium oxide and subjected to thermogravimetric studies. The nickel complex was stable upto 180° whereas that of cobalt started decomposing at 85°.

Effect of pH and concentration of the reagent : The pH ranges for quantitative precipitation were 6.4-6.9 for nickel and 6.7-12.0 for cobalt. For the former, at least three times the reagent theoretically calculated, were required, while the same for cobalt was three and half times.

Effect of sequestering agents : The determination of nickel or cobalt was possible in the presence of fluoride or sulphosalicylate. Phosphate and tartrate had no adverse effect in the precipitation of nickel though masked cobalt partially. Nitri-lotriacetate, ethylenediamine tetraacetate, cyanide,

ethylenediamine, citrate or thioglycolate, prevented the precipitation of both nickel and cobalt.

Effect of diverse ions : The presence of arsenate or molybdate did not interfere with the estimation of nickel or cobalt. Sulphosalicylic acid was used to mask iron (III), manganese (II) and vanadyl ions in case of both cobalt and nickel as well as for the separation of nickel from chromium or cobalt from aluminium. Sodium potassium tartrate was used to mask iron(III), chromium(III), manganese(II), bismuth(III), tin(II), antimony(III) or molybdenum(IV) in the determination of nickel. The results of these separations are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF NICKEL AND COBALT FROM DIVERSE IONS

Metal ion (mg)	Diverse ion (mg)	Masked by	Metal ion found (mg)	Rel. error (%)
Ni ²⁺ , 14.37	Fe ³⁺ ; 20	a	14.22 ; 14.29	-1.03 ; -0.62
	Fe ³⁺ ; 30	b	14.29 ; 14.35	-0.52 ; -0.10
	Cr ³⁺ ; 15	a	14.31 ; 14.32	-0.38 ; -0.31
	Cr ³⁺ ; 15	b	14.37 ; 14.39	nil ; +0.14
	Mn ²⁺ ; 30	a	14.23 ; 14.22	-0.94 ; -1.01
	Mn ²⁺ ; 15	b	14.26 ; 14.29	-0.73 ; -0.52
	Sn ²⁺ ; 30	a	14.25 ; 14.32	-0.80 ; -0.31
	Sb ³⁺ ; 30	a	14.29 ; 14.31	-0.52 ; -0.38
	Bi ³⁺ ; 30	a	14.35 ; 14.37	-0.10 ; nil
	MoO ₄ ²⁺ ; 15	a	14.32 ; 14.37	-0.31 ; nil
	VO ³⁺ ; 10	b	14.22 ; 14.25	-1.01 ; -0.80
	AsO ₄ ³⁻ ; 30	—	14.39 ; 14.37	+0.14 ; nil
MoO ₄ ²⁻ ; 15	—	14.21 ; 14.29	-1.08 ; -0.52	
Co ²⁺ , 9.60	Al ³⁺ ; 30	b	9.52 ; 9.55	-0.85 ; -0.53
	Fe ³⁺ ; 5	b	9.54 ; 9.48	-0.64 ; -1.21
	Mn ²⁺ ; 10	b	9.51 ; 9.57	-0.92 ; -0.32
	VO ³⁺ ; 10	b	9.57 ; 9.59	-0.32 ; -0.12
	AsO ₄ ³⁻ ; 30	—	9.58 ; 9.58	-0.26 ; -0.26
	MoO ₄ ²⁻ ; 60	—	9.54 ; 9.57	-0.64 ; -0.32

(a) tartrate ; (b) sulphosalicylate.

However the relative error was too high (>1%) when iron or chromium was present in large excess. For such mixtures, e. g. in case of stainless steel, preliminary separation using ion-exchangers was necessary.

Standard deviation : The relative standard deviation for 30 determinations for each of the metals were $\pm 0.46\%$ for nickel and $\pm 0.45\%$ for cobalt.

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